

Investigating entrepreneurship levels of pre-service music teachers

Rasim Erol Demirbatır

Department of Fine Arts, Bursa Uludağ University, Turkey

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to examine the entrepreneurship levels of Pre-Service Music Teachers (Bursa Uludağ University Faculty of Education Music Teaching Undergraduate Program students) in terms of gender, grade level and career goals. For this purpose, data were collected from all 1st and 4th year students studying at Bursa Uludağ University Faculty of Education, Department of Music Education. The Individual Entrepreneurship Perception Scale (IEPS) and a Personal Information Form were used to collect the data. Mann Whitney U test was used to analyze the data. In line with the findings obtained, it was found that there was no significant difference in terms of IEPS total and subscale scores by gender. However, there were significant differences in favor of 4th year students in terms of locus of control, self-confidence and self-discipline sub-scores, as well as the total IEPS scores by grade level. It was concluded that those aiming for a non-teaching profession got significantly higher locus of control scores than those aiming to become a teacher. Regarding these results, suggestions have been developed to increase the entrepreneurship level of pre-service music teachers.

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Corresponding Author:

Rasim Erol Demirbatır
Department of Fine Arts
Bursa Uludağ University
Görükle Kampusu, 16059 Nilüfer/Bursa, Turkey
Email: redemir@uludag.edu.tr

1. INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship is not only an economic value but also a social and cultural phenomenon. Parallel to its role in the economic process, it is the initiator of a transformational/innovative process in the social structure [1]. It can be defined as putting forward different actions in order to obtain monetary gain and personal satisfaction by taking financial, psychological, and social risks in order to put the necessary time and effort into a common definition. Encouraging and developing entrepreneurship is a very important economic and social responsibility area where higher education institutions are expected to contribute.

It is becoming more and more important today that higher education institutions turn into entrepreneurial institutions that provide environment, culture, practices and opportunities to increase the entrepreneurship levels of their students and graduates [2]. Because entrepreneurship refers to an expected equipment to be able to deal with a world full of confusion, uncertainty and opportunities. There is a dynamism in the world where job and occupational status are constantly changing. It will provide many advantages for higher education graduates to equip themselves with innovative and creative skills that will empower them against the diverse challenges of the global system [3]. Entrepreneurship can equip them with the skills they need to adapt to a dynamic environment. In addition, raising people who can create new job opportunities in countries with high economic problems and unemployment is also important in terms of

social and economic benefits as well as individual benefits. Entrepreneurship can equip them with the skills they need to adapt to a dynamic environment [4]. The current literature on entrepreneurship emphasizes that beyond business entrepreneurship, entrepreneurship can be mentioned in different areas such as social, lifestyle, corporate, artistic, intellectual, and educational entrepreneurship [4], [5].

Despite all the benefits of entrepreneurship seen in relation to the transformation of individuals and systems, paradigms and society [4], the role of higher education institutions in the development of entrepreneurship has only recently begun to be considered important [6]. One of the reasons for this is that higher education institutions are not able to turn to entrepreneurship training without sufficient knowledge in this field. Because entrepreneurship research started to gain momentum only from the middle of the 20th century. Today, the role of higher education institutions by teaching entrepreneurship, transferring knowledge and innovation to businesses and how students should develop this role in the future is an area that is discussed with great importance and a lot of research needs to be done. In connection with this, today as in the world and in Turkey, entrepreneurship education in higher education institutions, not only for economic and administrative sciences faculty students, has become one of the important issues for students of all faculties. Many universities provide their students with courses, programs and degrees in entrepreneurship. It is reported in the literature that music education students are among the groups that can benefit most from the entrepreneurship curriculum [7].

Considering that the students of the Music Teaching Undergraduate Program are trained to become music teachers at various levels of national education, it may be difficult to understand the importance of the concept of "entrepreneurship" for these students at first. However, in addition to being teachers in schools, most of the students studying in these programs have many options such as working in "out-of-school" environments, providing music education in other institutions or specifically, working for performance, dealing with the commercial aspect of music. It can be said that people who have received professional music education have a wide range of work because of the individual, social, cultural, economic and educational functions of music-related phenomena in human life. In this respect, it seems possible that entrepreneurship training in music education can create both individual and social value [4].

Although music educators and musicians do not usually see themselves as entrepreneurs, creativity, passion, self-confidence, and perseverance can be considered as some of the main characteristics of both music people and entrepreneurs [8]. In addition, some skills defined by professional musicians as essential components of their careers [9]; adaptability, resourcefulness, and the ability to multitask are also features in the entrepreneur's skill set [8]. Therefore, in addition to emphasizing the different values of art entrepreneurship, it is beneficial to emphasize common features in both dimensions.

It is reported in the literature that students studying in the field of music education cannot always build or continue a musical career after graduation [10] and that entrepreneurship education is seen as a way to equip these students with the necessary knowledge and skills to prepare them for different career options in the field of music [11]. With entrepreneurship trainings, significant contributions can be made to the preparation of music education students for the business world [12] and to increase their employability [13]. However, in order to provide more effective training in this field, some pioneering research is needed to shed light on how these trainings can be done. In the literature, it is emphasized that there is no consensus on the best practice among the various trainings regarding the effectiveness of different entrepreneurship trainings provided for music education students, and the evidence showing both short and long term effectiveness of these trainings is not at a sufficient level [11], [14]. In addition, although undergraduate students indicate the need to participate in entrepreneurship education, it is also observed that they do not always appreciate, prioritize, or show interest in these trainings [15]. In this respect, examining the various variables related to the entrepreneurship levels of music education students becomes important as it will contribute to the identification of students who may need more entrepreneurship education programs to be provided.

In this study, it is aimed to examine the entrepreneurship levels of pre-service music teachers (Bursa Uludağ University Education Faculty Music Teaching Undergraduate Program students) in terms of gender, grade level and career goals. It is expected that the findings obtained will not only contribute to revealing the status of pre-service music teachers in terms of their individual entrepreneurship perception levels, but also shed light on the arrangement of services to increase the entrepreneurship levels of pre-service music teachers.

In the research, answers to the following questions were sought: 1) Do pre-service music teachers' perception of individual entrepreneurship total and subscale scores differ significantly by gender?; 2) Do pre-service music teachers' perception of individual entrepreneurship differ significantly according to their total and subscale entrepreneurship scores at the 1st and 4th grade levels?; 3) Do pre-service music teachers' perception of individual entrepreneurship total and subscale scores differ significantly according to their career goals?

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Participants

Within the scope of the research, data were collected from 82 students between the ages of 18-33 ($M=20.68$, $SD=2.73$) who were studying in the 1st and 4th years of Bursa Uludağ University Faculty of Education Music Education Undergraduate Program in the fall semester of the 2019-2020 academic year. The 70.7% ($N=58$) of the participants were female and 29.3% ($N=24$) of them were male. Distribution of 1st and 4th years students across gender groups is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of 1st and 4th years students across gender groups

		Gender		Total	Percent
		Male	Female		
Grade	1 st Year	29	11	40	70.7
Level	4 th Year	13	29	42	29.3
Total		58	24	82	100.0

2.2. Data collection tools

2.2.1. Individual entrepreneurship perception scale (IEPS)

It is a 5-point Likert type measuring instrument consisting of 31 items to measure the perception of entrepreneurship [16]. The results of the exploratory factor analysis performed with the data obtained from university students in order to examine the construct validity of the IEPS showed that the scale consists of 6 dimensions (Planning, Locus of Control, Self-Confidence, Communication, Motivation and Self-discipline), explaining 53.32% of the total variance. The loads given by the items to the dimensions for the IEPS range between .30 and .74. In addition, the significant difference found between the individual entrepreneurship perception levels of the students who have and did not receive entrepreneurship training provided evidence that the scale has a satisfactory level of construct validity [16]. In the same study, the Cronbach-alpha coefficient was calculated in order to examine the internal consistency of the IEPS was .92 for the scale in general, and .80, .84, .75, .72 for the Planning, Locus of Control, Self-Confidence, Communication, Motivation and Self-Discipline sub-dimensions, respectively. It was found to be .75 and .60. Within the scope of this study, the recalculated Cronbach-alpha values on the data obtained from the students of the music education department were .89 for the whole scale. Planning, Locus of Control, Self-Confidence, Communication, Motivation and Self-Discipline sub-dimensions are .70, .70, .68, .62, .66, .74 respectively.

2.2.2. Personal information form

It was prepared by the researcher in order to determine the personal characteristics of the participants in the study. The form contains four questions regarding the age, gender, year and career goals (teaching music or a profession other than teaching) of the participants.

2.3. Process

The data were collected from the students who volunteered to participate in the research in the spring semester of the 2019-2020 academic year, before or at the end of the class hours, in sessions of approximately 10 minutes each. In the practices, the purpose of the study was explained to the students, and information was given on volunteerism regarding participation in the study and the confidentiality of personal information.

2.4. Data analysis

Before data analysis, the normality of data was checked by using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test and skewness and kurtosis values. Results are presented in Table 2.

As seen in Table 2, the data did not show a normal distribution. As a result, the Mann Whitney U test was used to examine the total and subscale scores of IEPS according to gender, grade level and career goals. Additionally, mean (X), standard deviation (Sd), percentage (%), frequency (f) were calculated. All analyzes were made using the SPSS 22 program. In all analyzes, the significance levels were taken as $p < .01$ and $p < .05$.

Table 2. Results of the kolmogorov-smirnov normality test and skewness and kurtosis values

Scale/sub-scale	Statistic	Sig.	Skewness	Kurtosis
Planning	.112	.013*	-.272	-.459
Locus of control	.129	.002**	-.395	.775
Confidence	.127	.002**	-.647	.791
Communication	.137	.001**	-.551	-.398
Motivation	.140	.000**	-.487	.372
Self-discipline	.132	.001**	-.573	.350

*p<.05

** p<.05

3. RESULTS

3.1. Findings regarding the examination of IEPS total and subscale scores by gender

The results of the Mann Whitney U test conducted in order to examine whether the IEPS total and subscale scores indicated a significant difference according to gender are given in Table 3.

As seen in Table 3, when looking at the results of the Mann Whitney U test, no significant difference was found between the total and sub-scale scores of IEPS by gender. Accordingly, there is no significant difference between female and male students in terms of both the individual entrepreneurship perception total score (U=661.00, p=.721), and in the subscale scores including; planning (U=676.00, p=.838), locus of control (U=660.50, p=.717), self-confidence (U=658.50, p=.70), communication (U=589.00, p=.269), motivation (U=625.00, p=.465) and self-discipline (U=595.00, p=.298).

Table 3. Mann Whitney U test results for examining the IEPS total and subscale scores by gender

Scale	Gender	N	Mean rank	Sum of ranks	Mann-Witney U	Z value	p
IEPS total	Female	58	42.10	2442.00	661.00	-.357	.721
	Male	24	40.04	961.00			
Planning	Female	58	41.16	2387.00	676.00	-.205	.838
	Male	24	42.33	1016.00			
Locus of control	Female	58	40.89	2371.50	660.50	-.363	.717
	Male	24	42.98	1031.50			
Confidence	Female	58	40.85	2369.50	658.50	-.385	.700
	Male	24	43.06	1033.50			
Communication	Female	58	43.34	2514.00	589.00	-1.106	.269
	Male	24	37.04	889.00			
Motivation	Female	58	42.72	2478.00	625.00	-.731	.465
	Male	24	38.54	925.00			
Self-discipline	Female	58	43.24	2508.00	595.00	-1.041	.298
	Male	24	37.29	895.00			

3.2. Findings regarding the examination of IEPS total and subscale scores by grade level

The results of the Mann Whitney U test, which was conducted to examine whether the total and subscale scores of IEPS displayed a significant difference according to the grade level are given in Table 4.

As it can be seen in Table 4, the IEPS total scores (U=603.00, p=.028), and sub-scores of locus of control (U=575.00, p=.014), self-confidence (U=604.00, p=.027) and self-discipline (U=618.50, p=.038) were found to be significantly different in favor of fourth grade students comparing to the 1st grade students. Accordingly, it can be said that the 4th grade music students perceive themselves more entrepreneurial than the 1st year students, in terms of locus of control, self-confidence and self-discipline. No significant difference was found between the 1st and 4th grade music students in terms of planning (U=630.00, p=.050), communication (U=633.50, p=.052) and motivation (U=795.50, p=.677) scores.

Table 4. The Mann Whitney U test results for examining the IEPS total and subscale scores according to grade level

Scale	Grade	N	Mean rank	Sum of ranks	Mann-Whitney U	Z value	p
IEPS total	1 st Grade	40	35.58	1423.00	603.00	-2.20	.028*
	4 th Grade	42	47.14	1980.00			
Planning	1 st Grade	40	36.25	1450.00	630.00	-1.958	.050
	4 th Grade	42	46.50	1953.00			
Locus of control	1 st Grade	40	34.88	1395.00	575.00	-2.467	.014*
	4 th Grade	42	47.81	2008.00			
Confidence	1 st Grade	40	35.60	1424.00	604.00	-2.205	.027*
	4 th Grade	42	47.12	1979.00			
Communication	1 st Grade	40	36.34	1453.50	633.50	-1.942	.052
	4 th Grade	42	46.42	1949.50			
Motivation	1 st Grade	40	42.61	1704.50	795.50	-.417	.677
	4 th Grade	42	40.44	1698.50			
Self-discipline	1 st Grade	40	35.96	1438.50	618.50	-2.078	.038*
	4 th Grade	42	46.77	1964.50			

*p<.05

3.3. Findings regarding the examination of IEPS total and subscale scores according to career goals

The results of the Mann Whitney U test, which was conducted to examine whether the IEPS total and subscale scores show a significant difference according to the career goal, are given in Table 5.

As seen in Table 5, when analyzed in terms of career goal; it was concluded that those aiming a non-teaching profession (M=51.78) got significantly higher locus of control (U=414.50, p=.026) points than those who aim to become teachers (M=38.19). Individual entrepreneurship perception total score (U=525.50, p=.307), planning (U=563.00, p=.536), self-confidence (U=480.50, p=.129), communication (U=615.00, p=.956), motivation (U=482.50, p=.134) and self-discipline (U=611.00, p=.922) scores did not differ significantly between those who aim to become teachers and those who aim for a career other than teaching.

Table 5. The Mann Whitney U test results for the examination of IEPS total and subscale scores according to career goals

Scale	Groups	N	Mean rank	Sum of ranks	Mann-Whitney U	Z value	p
IEPS total	Teaching	62	39.98	2478.50	525.50	-1.021	.307
	Non-teaching	20	46.23	924.50			
Planning	Teaching	62	40.58	2516.00	563.00	-.619	.536
	Non-teaching	20	44.35	887.00			
Locus of control	Teaching	62	38.19	2367.50	414.50	-2.227	.026*
	Non-teaching	20	51.78	1035.50			
Confidence	Teaching	62	39.25	2433.50	480.50	-1.517	.129
	Non-teaching	20	48.48	969.50			
Communication	Teaching	62	41.42	2568.00	615.00	-.055	.956
	Non-teaching	20	41.75	835.00			
Motivation	Teaching	62	43.72	2710.50	482.50	-1.500	.134
	Non-teaching	20	34.63	692.50			
Self-discipline	Teaching	62	41.35	2564.00	611.00	-.098	.922
	Non-teaching	20	41.95	839.00			

*p<.05

4. DISCUSSION

In this study, the entrepreneurship levels of pre-service music teachers were examined in terms of gender, grade level (1st and 4th grades), and career goals (career targeting teaching or other than teaching). First of all, it was seen in the study that there was no significant difference by gender in terms of

entrepreneurship total and sub-dimension scores of these students. In the literature, it is seen that studies in which entrepreneurship is dealt with by gender draw attention to the subject from many different angles. For example, although the number of women entrepreneurs in the world is increasing gradually [17], the number of male entrepreneurs still seems much more than women. It is reported that [18] males prefer to do their own business more than females, and among adolescents, males tend to engage in entrepreneurial activities more than females [19], [20]. However, it has been revealed in the literature that this situation can be affected by many cognitive, motivational and environmental factors starting from skills and competencies [21]. In addition, it is seen that the sectors where women and men use their entrepreneurship and the ways of using their entrepreneurship are different [22].

The common belief in Turkey is that the teaching profession is one of the professions in which mostly women work. As a matter of fact, approximately 71% of the participants, who constitute the working group of this research and consist of all the 1st and 4th year students attending Bursa Uludağ University Music Teaching Undergraduate Program, were also women students. The finding of this study that the entrepreneurship levels of Pre-Service Music Teachers do not differ by gender seems consistent with the findings of the studies in the literature showing that there are no significant differences among university students in terms of gender in the perception of their entrepreneurship skills [23]-[28]. Accordingly, as a result of this study, it can be said that male and female music teacher candidates perceive themselves as entrepreneurs at the same level. It is thought that the lack of a significant difference between the entrepreneurship levels of men and women who came together to receive education in a teacher-training institution can be explained by the fact that individuals with similar intentions and personal characteristics, despite the gender difference, come together in these educational institutions. However, if other studies are conducted to monitor the same individuals after graduation, it can be examined whether the entrepreneurship levels of male and female music teachers change due to other factors in the future.

This study also found some significant differences between the entrepreneurship levels of the Pre-Service Music Teachers in the 1st and 4th grade. First of all, in terms of entrepreneurship total score, it was observed that 4th grade students got significantly higher scores than 1st grade students. In addition, 4th grade students' scores in terms of locus of control, self-confidence and self-discipline dimensions of entrepreneurship were found to be significantly higher than the scores of 1st year students. In other words, senior music education students reported that they were more entrepreneurial than 1st grade music education students. This shows that, during their undergraduate studies at this faculty, students generally improve their entrepreneurship level, and in particular at the level of locus of control, self-confidence, and self-discipline. These findings, which show the contribution of the education they received to the entrepreneurship levels of pre-service music teachers, are pleasing in a way that they show the positive effects of the music education already provided in this program on the entrepreneurship levels of the teacher candidates.

However, in this study, no significant differences were found between 1st and 4th grade music teacher candidates in terms of planning, communication, and motivation sub-dimensions of entrepreneurship. There are studies in the literature showing that entrepreneurship does not change significantly according to grade level [23]. This situation can be explained by the fact that the students who started this program to receive music education are at a high level in terms of planning, communication and motivation at the beginning, and it may also mean that they do not develop in these areas from the 1st to the last year. Since it will be important for music teacher educators to know the advantages or shortcomings of music teaching students in terms of planning, communication and motivation, it is important to carry out other studies in order to fully understand this situation.

Finally, in this study, it was concluded that in terms of career goals pre-service music teachers who aim to be a teacher have significantly higher locus of control scores than those who aim to become teachers. However, no significant difference was found neither in the total scores of entrepreneurship nor in the sub-scores of planning, self-confidence, communication, motivation and self-discipline of those who aim to become teachers and those who aim for a non-teaching profession. Accordingly, those who aim for a teaching or non-teaching career for the overall and all sub-dimensions of entrepreneurship (planning, self-confidence, communication, motivation, and self-discipline) reported similar characteristics. However, these two groups differed significantly from each other in terms of locus of control. In this way, the locus of control among the sub-dimensions of entrepreneurship, music teacher students' career goals are affected by factors that are not in their hands to control many additional conditions, or in other words, pre-service teachers who believe in their own power to control conditions should try different career options. It has been interpreted as they are more eager about it. It is thought that this finding will contribute to the determination of the content of career counselling and/or entrepreneurship training programs to be given to pre-service music teachers.

In this study, the entrepreneurship levels of pre-service music teachers were discussed only in terms of three demographic variables such as gender, grade level and career goals. There are many other variables

that can affect the entrepreneurship levels of pre-service music teachers. For example, Keleş, *et al.* [29] reported significant differences between the entrepreneurship levels of students who study at foundations and state universities, with or without family businesses, or with and without work experience. Similarly, the entrepreneurship levels of pre-service music teachers can be examined in future studies in terms of students' work experiences and some characteristics of their families. In addition, dealing with the interactions of these variables with each other through different analyzes such as mediation/moderation analysis or structural equation modeling will further contribute to the literature in terms of understanding the factors that play a role on the entrepreneurship levels of music education students in relation to each other.

The findings of this study are limited only to the 1st and 4th year students of Bursa Uludağ University Faculty of Education Music Teaching Undergraduate Program. To increase the generalizability of findings, music teaching programs from different universities in Turkey is advisable to collect data from students attending degree programs.

5. CONCLUSION

This study revealed that the entrepreneurship levels of pre-service music teachers do not differ according to gender, but 4th grade students have higher entrepreneurship levels compared to 1st grade students, and music teaching students who aim for a non-teaching music career are internally controlled compared to those who aim for a teaching career. These results have contributed to the literature in terms of showing that continuing a music teaching program has a positive effect on the entrepreneurship levels of students, based on the example of Bursa Uludağ University Music Teaching Program. In addition, it has shown that in order to develop career goals other than music teaching, these students may need career counseling services so that they have internal locus of control instead of external locus of control.

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BIOGRAPHY OF AUTHOR

Dr. Rasim Erol Demirbatır is a lecturer at Bursa Uludağ University Faculty of Education, Department of Fine Arts Education. He holds Ph.D. Degree in Music Education from the Gazi University in Turkey. He continues his research in various fields of music education.